

Possession of Money

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ABSTRACT: The relationship between humans and nature is inevitable, it is a direct cause-and-effect relationship. Natural human relationships are characterized by human-to-human communication. People are products of each other in communication, so human communication is free. Inevitability in natural relations becomes freedom in human communication. Freedom in human communication is creativity. Creativity makes people differentiate into subjects and products. Internal products correspond to standards, external products correspond to money. Human communication becomes the standard exchange, money is social. Social life is about buying and selling labor goods. Labor trading makes free communication mandatory, forced by standards and money. Having standards, not knowing how much money is enough, always feeling like it's lacking, and not knowing how to stop, that's the instinct and habits of playing the piano. When money is the exclusive object of human possession, buyers and sellers appear. The seller needs money, and the buyer has money. The money instinct appears, making life coerced by money. Freedom to care for and help each other becomes a service, serving money. Serving money becomes serving those who have money; without money, you cannot be served. Human discrimination appears. Eliminating discrimination is not the eradication of humans, it is the eradication of non-human forces.

KEYWORDS: Society, money, norms, economics, politics

1. INTRODUCTION

From each according to one's ability, to each according to one's needs is a real society, it is different from a utopian society. But real society has not yet become an object of scientific research. Social research does not originate from reality, but from aspirations, dreams, and ideals that are considered constitutions and contributions to initiatives that become the building of a utopian society. Real society takes people as the measure, people do not discriminate. The utopian society uses standards and money as a measure, so people are discriminated against. Building a utopian society becomes the profession of dogmatic theoretical scientists, while the richness of real society becomes the richness and diversity of different professions. Real society is not the society that will be, but the society that is. Each person living according to their abilities and needs is life's happiness. Building an ideal society in the future is not about dividing happiness equally for all generations, but it is about using one person as a means for the other. The article titled The Possession of Human Money contributes to clarifying the division of labor and distribution in the process of social development.

2. RESEARCH OVERVIEW

Money is studied from many different angles, especially from an economic perspective. Money becomes a measure of social development, living standards, and enjoyment. Income level becomes a measuring stick between countries with different traditions, canons, laws, and regulations. Money has become a real, tangible force that popularly governs human life and is studied and presented from quite a variety of perspectives. In it, "Money is the visible spirit, the transformation of all human and natural attributes into their opposite, the confusion and universal distortion of things; it carries out the intimate combination of things that cannot be combined" (Marx and Engels, 42, P. 213), "money is a truly creative force" (Marx and Ph. Engels, 42, P.214). first). Money universally regulates nature, society, and thinking. However, the acquisition and inheritance of this scientific argument from a philosophical perspective is still limited. The article titled Money Possess People not only continues the inheritance but also clarifies it from the perspective of human philosophy.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The content of the article is titled Social Development Approached from Human Philosophical Methodology. Humans are the subject of perception and the object of perception. All things and phenomena exist in two basic forms: inside and outside humans. Social life is rich but only exists in those two forms. One is that society is within people, people live by society, and it manifests itself in

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different abilities in work, profession, and employment positions. Second, society is outside of humans, so society is human needs. If society is not a human need, then society is meaningless, its existence is redundant. People satisfy society to survive and become a society that promotes people. It is a society that maximizes the use of different potentials and resources for development. People are the measure, everyone is equal. When standards and money are used to measure people, society discriminates between noble and lowly, rich and poor.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Society

Natural human communication is direct cause and effect. People are direct products of each other, so human communication is free, creative, and non-profit. When communicating, people use products as intermediaries, which is society, which is coercion, instinct, and self-interest. Natural functions become social tasks. The social task of division of labor becomes the purchase and sale of labor goods. Trade goods are expressed in terms of standards or money. Making money through labor is performing an economic function. The amount of money earned by job placement is a political mandate. Economic functions become political tasks. The transformation between economics and politics in means and ends has a specific historical nature. Economics determines politics, manifested in the power of money, while politics determines economics, manifested in the power of standards.

Standards are internal, money is external to people. The internal and external balance of the person becomes the standard exchange of money. The norm, money as a commodity in trading, became popular. All social life activities are dominated by goods. Human life has a transformation between standards and money, which becomes a transformation between economics and politics in social life. Society outside people is people inside society and vice versa. People and society are merged into one, without distinction.

When society is independently and metaphysically separated from humans in perception, humans, and society have a distinction, they become objects of each other. Human abilities are society's needs and vice versa. The possibility and need for unity are reality, truth, it is satisfaction. Inconsistency in needs and abilities is helplessness and unhappiness. Human helplessness is society's misfortune and vice versa. Satisfying needs is instinct and possession. Satisfying abilities are creativity and differentiation. Human possession of society is an instinct, and creativity is social differentiation. The richness of social life becomes the richness of work and career. The richness of jobs and careers is the promotion and maximum exploitation of different human resources. Maximize human potential and resources for the survival of society.

Society is a product of people, people live by society. Human survival is the goal, society is the means. When society is a living object, it becomes a purpose. Humans are the means for the existence of society. A society without people is meaningless. When people are lost, society becomes redundant. People become objects of social possession. The society promotes, exploits, and takes advantage of people by standards, money is the possession of people. Society is the subject that owns, exploits, and uses people for what society wants. Society's appropriation of people creates diversity in forms of ownership and occupations in a certain economic system.

4.2. Economic system

People are the abilities and needs of society. Satisfying abilities are creativity, and differentiation into subjects and products, which are privately owned. Satisfying needs is instinct, possessing products for survival, that is private individuals. The difference between privately owned and private individuals in the process of differentiation makes society rich in objects, forms of ownership, occupations, job positions, living standards, and employment. enjoy. The population is larger, and the diversity of ownership and professions becomes a diversity of private economic sectors (privately - owned), private economic (private individual), collective economy, state economy; and diversity of occupations in industry, agriculture, and services. The richness of labor, occupations, and job positions becomes the richness of behavior, which is the richness of society.

The owners, jobs, professions, and different job positions in the assignment of functions and tasks in a specific historical economic system are all the same people. People are the same, but the diversity of ownership forms, economic sectors, economic sectors, distribution diversity, and different levels of enjoyment become the richness of life. Depending on their abilities and needs, they can choose different jobs, occupations, and positions to become farmers, workers, intellectuals, doctors, engineers, teachers, and civil servants, businessmen, clergy in agriculture, industry, services, religion, government, companies, banks. Choosing a way of life that suits your abilities and needs is the reality, the truth about living people. The richness of society is the richness of ownership, the diversity of occupations, the richness of abilities, and the needs become different between people.

Human discrimination begins with the purchase and sale of labor goods. Selling labor means buying jobs. Jobs and labor that meet certain standards can be sold, and money must be enough to buy labor. Sellers need money and buyers have money. Privately owned sells labor to buy jobs, while private individuals buy labor to sell jobs. Privately owned constantly improves qualifications, expertise, and skills to meet standards. Private individuals constantly speculate, accumulate capital, and have enough money. The transfer of ownership of goods in buying and selling makes differences between rich and poor, noble and lowly. Buying and selling goods and shifting the economic system cause division in society, with one part having both standards and money; a part has money but no standards; a part that has standards but no money; a part that has no money and no standards.

The transformation of the economic system is measured by the amount of reciprocal money, satisfaction is measured by standards.

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Money and standards manifest in career and job positions. Any profession that still has the ability and needs of society will have the conditions to exist and develop. Any profession that no longer has the ability and needs becomes individual and disappears. The professions are subject to each other, they both cooperate and compete with each other. Not only do professions of coercion, domination, and management appear, but they also shift from agriculture, industry, manufacturing, and processing to services, serving in health care, education, employment, and investment, import-export trading. Competitive industries and comparative advantages are exploited to maximize their potential and strengths for social development.

The occupational structure is expanded or narrowed depending on abilities and social needs. Selling labor is buying jobs, and creating jobs to sell is labor trading. The labor business is buying and selling people to become a job market, exploiting different resources to the maximum. A career that doesn't match your abilities is powerless, a job position that doesn't satisfy your needs is unhappiness. Helplessness and unhappiness become fake at work, which is poor quality labor goods. Overcome the situation of poor quality labor by standardizing occupations and jobs at levels, expertise, and skills.

The family must comply with tradition, religion must comply with canon law, the state must comply with the law, and companies and banks must comply with charters. With a large population, if any profession has a better life than other professions, poor quality labor will appear in that economic area. Falsehood in the profession becomes falsehood in all species, that is, falsehood in family, religion, state, company, or bank. Falsehood becomes widespread, causing species to self-destruct. Species are human needs and abilities, then that species exists and develops. Any species that no longer has human capabilities or needs will die.

Humans become objects of each other's survival, causing society to differentiate into different species. Different abilities and needs become the habits and life instincts of different species. Each species has its behavior, different needs, and abilities in exchange. Whichever species still has the ability and need for that species survives, and whichever species no longer has the ability or need for that species perishes. In an economic system, species are the subjects of each other's living. There is no distinction between good and evil, fairness and injustice in work or career, but there is a distinction between truth and falsehood in life. occupation, job position, that is, quality and poor quality labor. Poor quality labor becomes unearned labor, and unearned labor becomes unearned. Laziness appears in the social division of labor and becomes the function of solving jobs, distributing, and regulating labor. Job creation and labor regulation become social management functions. Differences in job management become job positions, and different living standards become different statuses in a political system.

4.3. Political system

People are the owners of products, society is the owner of people, that is, possessing, determining, using, exploiting, and promoting people in all different forms into things. society wants. Society possesses people by standards, money is a common phenomenon, it is not only a division of labor and social tasks but also mutual ownership between people. Mutual ownership means using each other for what we want together. Spouses, parents, and children use each other to do what the family wants. Clergy use each other for what religion wants, civil servants use each other for what the government wants, and businessmen use each other for what the company wants.

But when the ends are different, one becomes the means used for the other's ends. With different job positions, incomes, and statuses in work management, the issue of ownership is raised between people. Husband and wife, parents, and children own each other through the tradition of family. Clergy own each other by canon law which is religion. Civil servants who own each other by law are the state. Businessmen own each other by charter as companies and banks. Humans live by their products, species live by possessing instincts. The survival instinct becomes a slave to tradition, canon law, law, charter, family, religion, state, company, and bank, that is, a slave to standards and money.

Promoting the human factor becomes exploiting the resources of family, religion, state, companies, and banks for social development. That is exploiting traditions, canons, laws, and regulations in the context of a commodity economy. Promoting different resources becomes exploiting different professions. Professions and properties with different origins become diverse economic sectors and industries, which is a diversity of survival habits in the process of development. The habit of social satisfaction is an instinct, it possesses standards and money but does not know enough, always feels lacking but does not know how to stop. Rich people still love money, noble people always have standards. The accumulation of capital and assets makes one part rich and the other part poor according to regulations. Rich and poor have different conditions, habits, and lifestyles. The behavior of one species becomes the way of life of another species. Whichever species still has the ability and need for that species to survive and develop. If a species no longer has the ability or need, that species will perish. Each species has different interests, purposes, and survival habits, becoming each other's living objects. Family, religion, state, company, bank, the objects of each other's survival become humans and the objects of humans. People use each other to become each other's tools and means perfectly.

People become objects of family life, religion, the state, companies, and banks. Any species that knows how to exploit, utilize, and promote humans effectively will survive. Any species that does not take humans as the object of its survival is the species that perishes. Species that exploit and promote human factors become possessive of humans. Possessing people means not knowing enough, always feeling lacking so you don't know how to stop. The possession of species by standards makes humans a suffering entity. When born, no one needs traditions, canons, laws, and regulations, but the coercion of norms makes species that comply with traditional habits, canons, laws, and regulations become species like family, religion, state, company, and bank. Species exploit

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humans by educating them according to the standards of that species. When a large population wants to work or find a job in a species, they educate, train, and train themselves according to the standards of that species to have a good life. work to do, have a job to live. Occupational diversity is the behavioral diversity of different species. Differences between species become differences between occupations measured by the amount of money earned, become differences in income levels and social status. Occupational discrimination becomes behavioral discrimination between species. Each species has a different way of living, which is the strength of each species.

The diversity of functions, tasks, job positions, and social status is diversity in standards. Diversity in standards is the richness of traditional resources, canons, laws, and regulations. Different species are living objects of each other. Species both cooperate and compete with each other regarding jobs, job positions, professions, status, standard of living, enjoyment, and income in the political system. The political system is the place where jobs, job positions, social status, and living standards are distributed with different ownership origins but are all the same people. Differences in enjoyment and living standards in the political system become differences in social status, that is, differences in rich and poor, noble and lowly, fair and unjust. Differences between people in the political system are differences in management fields, job positions, status, and income, making society divided by money. Money becomes the measure of the political system.

4.4. Labor trading becomes money trading

Free labor in any form is genuine, there is no discrimination against labor, but there are differences in labor ownership, labor products, work efficiency, and labor attributes. dynamic and expressed in labor prices. All professions are respected and equal, society does not discriminate between people. There is discrimination in the quality of labor expressed in the price of labor, so there is discrimination in society. There is no injustice in labor, there is only a difference between free labor and forced labor. Forced labor prevents people from fully and comprehensively developing themselves. Human values are universal, but labor prices depend on living conditions and circumstances. Labor is determined by the price of money, which becomes a commodity, that can be bought and sold, all exchanged. Labor trading is the exchange of value, quality, and human attributes. Cooperation, solidarity, tolerance, and openness in human communication are the civilized lifestyle of modern society. Social development becomes business, buying and selling labor, goods, and money in today's conditions.

Buying and selling goods and labor makes money the dominant alien force. All thoughts, labor, occupation, job position, and standard of living are determined by money. Money dictates, determines, possesses, and uses people for what money wants. Money is a common living object that causes the money instinct to appear. Life is measured by the amount of money in return. Differences in society use money as a measure. Social life has a money instinct, so the function of solving jobs and managing society by standards becomes a money service. Selling standards and buying money causes traditions, canons, laws, and regulations to be deformed. Differences in standards in the division of labor and job positions are reflected in labor prices. Money is the ubiquitous visible force that governs nature, society, and thinking. Resources are depleted due to money, improving the ecological environment when money is available. Wars, riots, protests, deception, and lies are caused by money. Thinking, invention and discovery manifest in productivity, economic efficiency, production costs, and product quality. 4.4. Labor trading becomes money trading

Wealth and poverty, nobility and vileness, good or bad, delinquency and dedication are measured in terms of money. The possession of money makes people become strangers to their fellow humans. People become cold and irresponsible, and the responsibility lies with money. The level of crime, dedication, and compensation for damage to reputation, honor, and dignity is measured by the amount of money as a counterpart. Money is a living object. Money becomes a possibility, a need for universal survival, causing the instinct for money to appear. Satisfying the need for money is an instinct, possessing money but not knowing enough, always feeling lacking but not knowing how to stop, makes people with a lot of money like money even more. Lust for money does not create a dull feeling, it is the instinct and behavior of money. The possession of money was not enough, so the money business appeared. Money trading became the buying and selling of domestic and foreign currencies, and foreign currency speculation appeared. Buying and selling domestic and foreign currencies means importing and exporting goods. Import and export of goods become import and export of labor. Labor import and export is the exchange and integration of different families, religions, states, companies, and banks globally. It is the mutual possession of people.

People are not only objects of possession of a country but also objects in international relations. International exchange and integration are requirements for trade in general, and trading in labor goods in particular. The business makes goods popular, a surplus of goods appears when old lifestyles are popularized, and new lifestyles are not created. Traditional values become the object of innovation and modernity. Modern nations develop based on exploiting the traditions of other nations. Relations between countries in development are human communication. But communicating with people with money in international relations becomes a money business, work in banks is an effective source of money income. Money trading in banks is not only domestic currency trading but also foreign currency trading and speculation. Trading and speculation in different currencies are popular. Currencies are special goods, they are exclusively issued products. The state's monopoly on money issuance becomes the profession of distributing, leading, and orienting social development.

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4.5. Competition for money becomes the possession of people

The state exists in all possible forms, one of which is the exclusive right to issue money, so business and money speculation are regulated and regulated by the state. But the money market is not completely regulated by the state, it also depends on many different factors such as production, purchasing power of goods, import and export, labor, speculation, and money trading. Money trading is a function of banks. The combination between the state and banks is tight, becoming the profession of issuing and trading money. The banking system complies with the state's laws and policies on money management, issuance, and trading. But careers in banking and government are all salaried workers. Protecting the value of domestic currency is a profession that involves dealing with foreign currencies. Dealing with foreign currencies becomes speculation and foreign currency trading. Competition for money in foreign currency trading appears. Buying, selling, circulating, and using foreign currency becomes the foreign affairs function of the state. The foreign affairs function becomes the function of business and foreign currency speculation. Speculation and use of foreign currencies have become popular in international relations.

Foreign currency trading and speculation became the import and export of goods in general. The existence of the state is not only determined by domestic currency but also by foreign currency. Foreign currency trading becomes a competition between states in the monopoly of money distribution. The loose and ineffective monetary policy allowed foreign currency to encroach, and the state's autonomy began to fade. Domestic currency and foreign currency are fiercely competitive goods. Business and money speculation are governed by the laws of supply and demand, value, and competition in international relations. Exchange, integration, and globalization make money a popular commodity. Any type of money corresponding to popular goods has socialization conditions, any type of money becomes individual, unique, and lost. The state is no longer the exclusive entity in issuing money; its existence depends on foreign currency. Society depends on imports and exports, national sovereignty is being coerced and invaded by foreign currency. Money business not only depends on the state's money management and issuance policies but it is also regulated by foreign currency market factors.

Competition between foreign currencies and domestic currencies depends on the social conditions of a country in international relations. States want their money issued to become a popular purchasing power in international relations. The purchasing power of money depends on many different factors. Any type of money that is required for life, capable of buying many goods, and that is multi-functional, then that type of money has the conditions to be popularized. The close combination in keeping the value of money becomes a systematic collusion between countries, it is the solidarity and cooperation of commercial and military organizations. Cooperation between countries in preserving the value of money becomes a mutual competition in issuing money. Wars about money are sometimes silent, covert, semi-open, and openly declared war. International trade and transactions become mutual possession of money. Speculation and trading of each other's money became uncontrolled production and issuance of money. Money speculation businesses become competitive, eliminating each other. Currencies are not abolished by various forms of money inflation. The existence of money becomes meaningless. People possessing money become money-possessing people. Without users, speculation makes money meaningless. The value of money comes when there are users and speculation. Money corresponds to the population using and speculating money. Money becomes the ability and need of the population. Dominating the population with money makes that money universal.

Competition for money becomes a war in today's conditions. The war of aggression for territory and competition for goods became a war of money. Any type of money that is no longer a requirement in business, speculation, or trading, that type of money will self-destruct. The destruction of money is the loss of the state's monopoly on issuing money. The demise of dictatorship in issuing money. The monopoly on issuing money is a political dictatorship. Eliminating political dictatorship means eliminating the monopoly on issuing money. Whichever type of currency is still in demand will continue to have conditions to be maintained and developed, and that type of currency will be issued. Money is common, money is inflationary, so money is a monopoly. Money is work and, career, money exists in every individual. Needing money becomes needing people. There is no one to possess or use money to cause inflation. Money is a universal means and universal power, it is a means. Money turns needs into simple possibilities. Money disappears on its own, a part that survives with money becomes poor according to regulations, and a part that has no money becomes rich by itself.

Little and much money are historically different. Science and technology become popular, productivity increases, the population does not increase, and the goods produced are surplus. Goods need people, and a large population becomes a requirement of commodity production. Creativity and production are requirements. A type of money that corresponds to humans appears, the change in the form of money is inevitable. The form of money that meets the universal human requirement is issued, that is universal human currency. Money corresponds to truth, so spending money is enjoying yourself with the truth of life. The war between currencies causes currencies to erase themselves from society. Truth is promoted, health is replaced by machines and robots; while resources and minerals are replaced by intelligence. Money causes instinctive forms of work to be replaced by machines and robots. The scarcity of resources and minerals is no longer a barrier to promoting the human factor. The transformation between physical, chemical, and biological energy makes humans the subject in the connection of all species and all things.

Different forms of money are strengthened by taking creative labor as their counterpart. The value of USD is not for self-consumption and enjoyment for countries that do not issue USD but for business and speculation. Speculation and reserves of USD

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make USD valuable. The USD value of a regime's assets is that regime guaranteed by USD. Countries that still speculate in USD, the remaining thing is that the dictatorship that issues USD is enriched by issuing USD. The issuance of USD is not inflationary while other countries still speculate in USD. All are turning all the world's wealth into a popular counterpart to the USD. Countries are being impoverished in terms of resources and people because of their USD wealth and dependence on it. The USD issuance regime is not perfect, the peak of all time, but its perfection is guaranteed by the strength of the USD. USD continues to be speculated to be larger in scale and nature. The USD issuance regime is guaranteed by the assets of the whole world. The USD non-speculation regime has become a unique phenomenon. But it must be admitted that the superiority of the USD is that the old abilities and needs are simply recreated, while the newly created abilities and needs are universal. The trend is still the dream of having a lot of USD. Countries that become rich when they issue money to finance hold all the world's wealth and assets, and institutions that speculate in USD have a lot of money that becomes the product of USD. Other institutions are making resources scarce by speculating and hoarding USD, causing humanity to fall into a state of value regression. Humanity became rich in money when USD became a piece of paper with a picture, printed with numbers, USD disappeared when real society became popular. USD is no longer issued by a monopoly but is a form of money that corresponds to the issuer. The special type of money produced and stored within each person is the final form of money's existence. If you like it, wealth will be revealed through creativity and if you don't like it, you will impoverish yourself with your instinctive fate. Wanting to make yourself poor is a special case, but getting rich through creativity is a personality in a real society.

5. CONCLUSION

Society is a product of humans, so the richness of humans is the richness of social life. The richness of social life is the richness of ownership and diversity of occupations in the division of labor and product distribution, but they are unified in a specific historical economic system. The richness of the economic system becomes the richness of job creation, labor redistribution, and labor regulation becomes social management. Social management appears to make different occupations in job positions and living standards become different in social status. Differences in social status become mutual property between people. One person is a means used for the other person's ends. Discrimination between people becomes discrimination between family, religion, state, company, and bank. The difference between family, religion, state, company, and bank is the difference between jobs, professions, job positions, and living standards, so there is discrimination between people. Eliminate human discrimination by regulating, managing, and assigning functions, tasks, and job positions so that everyone has the same opportunity to have a job. The political system has the functions of regulation, labor, distribution of benefits, and social security. But when money is a dictatorial object in possessing people, division in the political system appears. The deformation of the political system is not only deformed by domestic currency but also deformed by foreign currency. Whichever type of money becomes the dominant force, the species that produces and issues that type of money becomes the historical subject in the process of globalization.

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